

Kinetics and mechanism of Mn^{II} catalysed oxidation of amino alcohols (AAL) by Ce^{IV} in aqueous nitric acid medium

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The kinetics and mechanism of Mn^{II} catalysed oxidation of amino alcohols by Ce^{IV} in aqueous nitric acid to produce form-aldehyde and ammonia under the conditions [AAL] >> [Ce^{IV}] at different temperatures (35°–50°) have been studied in 2.5 mol dm⁻³ nitric acid media, the experimentally observed rate law conforms to

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = kK[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{AAL}][\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]/1 + K[\text{AAL}] + K[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$$

The fractional order dependence in both [AAL] as well as [Mn^{II}] indicates the formations of amino alcohol-Mn^{III} complex, Mn^{III} being active catalytic species, which has been confirmed by the shift in absorption maximum of Mn^{II} from 300 nm to 350 nm. The neutral Ce(NO₃)₄(H₂O)₂ is assumed to be reactive species in the oxidation of amino alcohols. The accelerating effect of [H⁺] is due to the formation of protonation of [Ce(NO₃)₄OH(H₂O)]⁻ species which is present in the reaction mixture. And to prevent the precipitation of Mn^{II} as MnO₂ high acid concentration (2.5 mol dm⁻³) was used in the present kinetic study.

In continuation of our earlier studies on metal ion¹ catalysed reaction by Ce^{IV} using different substrates in different acid media, we present here the mechanistic aspects of the title reaction. In fact several researchers studied on oxidation of amino alcohols by different oxidizing agents such as Cr^{VI}, hexacyanoferrate(III) periodate, chloramine-T (CLT)⁵ and Bi^{V2}. And few kinetic studies were reported on Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of amino alcohols by one and two electron oxidizing agents such as *N*-boromosuccinamide (NBS) hexacyanoferrate(III) and proposed different mechanisms³. Hence it was thought worthwhile to undertake title investigation in order to establish the mechanism of the oxidation reaction.

Results and discussion

Under the reaction conditions at [HNO₃] = 2.5, [Mn^{II}] = 2.0 × 10⁻¹ and [AAL] = 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm³ the rate of disappearance of Ce^{IV} shows a first order dependence on [Ce^{IV}] upto 75–85%. The plot of log [Ce^{IV}] vs time was linear. The observed pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*¹) are independent of the initial concentration of Ce^{IV} in 2.0 to 5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ range.

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \text{ or } -d \ln [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k^1 \quad (1)$$

At fixed [Ce^{IV}] and [Mn^{II}] the order in [AAL] is found to be fractional as obtained from the slopes of linear plot of log *k*¹ vs log [AAL] over the concentration range of 2.5 ×

10⁻² to 1.25 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³. These reactions were studied at [HNO₃] = 2.5 mol dm⁻³ and [Ce^{IV}] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

In the absence of Mn^{II} the reaction was sluggish under the present kinetic conditions and there was no correlations for the uncatalysed path. Rao *et al.* studied⁴ Mn^{II} catalysed oxidation reaction of aliphatic amines by Ce^{IV} in HNO₃ media and reported that in the present reaction conditions, Ce^{IV} known to oxidise Mn^{II} as shown below

Mn^{III} being unstable and it will further undergo auto-oxidation as :

But it can exist only in aqueous solution as part of a complex. In most of the cases Mn^{IV} gets precipitated as MnO₂ under the concentrated acid medium. At constant [AAL] and [Ce^{IV}] the rate of the reaction sharply increases with the increase in [Mn^{II}] and order in [Mn^{II}] was found to be fractional.

At constant ionic strength the rate dependence on [H⁺] was studied in the range of [H⁺] = 0.5–5.0 mol dm⁻³. Under the reaction conditions such as [Ce^{IV}] = 3 × 10⁻³, [Mn^{II}] = 2.0 × 10⁻¹, [AAL] = 3.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at 30° for [H⁺]

= 0.5, 1.00, 1.50, 2.00, 2.5 mol dm⁻³ the corresponding 10⁵ k¹ values are 5.4, 7.03, 7.30, 10.0, 14.4, 16.3, for ethanolamine. Similar effects were observed in the oxidation of propanolamine, diethanolamine and triethanolamine. The constant ionic strength was maintained by the addition of required amount of KNO₃ solution to the reaction mixture. Acceleration effect of [H⁺] can be explained in terms of existence of active reactive species of Ce(NO₃)₄(H₂O)₂ as below,

Formation of free radical was tested by adding acrylonitrile which undergoes polymerization. Under the experimental conditions, [Ce^{IV}] = 3.0 × 10⁻³, [H⁺] = 2.5 and [Mn^{II}] = 2.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, the rate of oxidations increased with increasing the temperature. This effect was studied in the temperature range 35–50°. Activation parameters were determined by using Eyring and Arrhenius equations. Further these parameters were used for structure-reactivity correlation which supported the proposed mechanism.

Mechanism of the reaction : Based on the experimental observations such as acrylonitrile test, stoichiometric studies and product analysis the probable reaction mechanism was as shown in Scheme 1. The homolytic bond fission of radical ion (HOCH₂CH₂CH₂ $\dot{\text{N}}^+\text{H}_2$) in step (8) leads to the formation of free radical which on further oxidation gives the product.

(where, AAL = ethanol amine, X = HOCH₂CH₂ $\dot{\text{N}}^+\text{H}_2$)

Scheme 1

The Mn^{II} catalysed oxidation reaction of AAL in aqueous nitric acid medium has been proposed through a complex formation between Mn^{III} and AAL. It was attributed that Mn^{III} can exist in the reaction mixture and readily forms the complex. The orders with respect to both [Mn^{II}] and [AAL] were fractional as obtained from the slope of

linear plot of log k¹ vs log [Mn^{II}] and log k¹ vs log [AAL] respectively. It was further supported by the shifting of absorption maximum of Mn^{II} from 300 to 350 nm, which is explained on the basis of complex formation between active catalytic species Mn^{III} and [AAL]. Under the experimental conditions like higher acidic medium and [Mn^{II}] >> [Ce^{IV}] it might be expected that there could be a more favourable conditions for the formation of Mn^{III} as shown in eq. (2) and it was assumed to be active catalytic species. Further the effect of [H⁺] and [NO₃⁻] on the rate of oxidation of aliphatic amines in the presence of Mn^{II} was well established⁶. The reactive species of oxidant assumed to be Ce(NO₃)₄(H₂O)₂ as in eq. (4) and catalytic species assumed was Mn^{III} as shown in the mechanism of Scheme 1.

Assuming the steady-state approximation for the reactive intermediate species i.e. (complex) the rate law could be as shown in eq. (16).

The kinetic features of the oxidation of all amino alcohols were similar but the reactivity of diethanolamine and triethanolamine was found to be higher due to availability of electrons at reactive site. Based on experimental studies such as acrylonitrile polymerization test, stoichiometric studies and product analysis the probable mechanism was proposed for diethanolamine is as shown in Scheme 2.

(where, S = diethanolamine, X = HOCH₂CH₂ $\dot{\text{N}}^+\text{HR}$ and RNH₂ = HOCH₂CH₂NH₂)

Scheme 2

The rate law for the oxidation of amino alcohols could be shown as below,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{kK [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{AAL}][\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{1 + K[\text{AAL}] + K[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]} \quad (16)$$

or

$$-2.303d \log_{10}[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k^1 = \frac{kK[\text{AAL}][\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{1 + K[\text{AAL}] + K[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]} \quad (17)$$

where k^1 is observed pseudo-first order rate constant, k is the rate constant for slow step shown eq. (7) or eq. (12) and K was the formation constant of the complex. Taking reciprocal of eq. (17) we get,

$$\frac{1}{k^1} = \frac{1}{[\text{AAL}]} \left[\frac{1}{kK[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]} + \frac{1}{k} \right] + \frac{1}{k[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]} \quad (18)$$

From the plots of $1/k^1$ vs $1/[\text{AAL}]$ at fixed $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ the values of K and k are evaluated for all the amino alcohols such as ethanolamine, propanolamine, diethanolamine and triethanolamine (Fig. 1). They are found to be $K = 1.83, 0.9, 19.4, 9.6$ and $k = 7.27, 19.6, 16, 40$ respectively. Units of K are $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, units of k are s^{-1} and the error limits in the formation constant and rate constants are $\pm 3\%$.

Fig. 1. Plot of $10^{-5}/k^1$ versus $10^{-1}/[\text{AAL}]$; $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 2.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 308 K.

The observed increase in the rate of oxidation of amino alcohols with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium

may be explained by the Eyring⁷ equation,

$$\ln k_{\text{D}} = \ln k_{\infty} + \frac{Z_{\text{D}}^2 \cdot e^2}{2k_{\text{B}} \cdot T D} \left[\frac{1}{r_{\text{B}}} - \frac{1}{r_{\neq}} \right]$$

where k_{D} and k_{∞} are the rate constants in the solvent medium of dielectric constants D and infinity respectively, r_{B} and r_{\neq} refer to radii of the reactant species and activated complex respectively. It is expected that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant when $r_{\neq} > r_{\text{B}}$. It is probable that radii of the activated complexes in the present cases are greater than the reactant molecules.

In the present study the order of reactivity was found to be triethanolamine > diethanolamine > propanolamine > ethanolamine. This indicates that polar effect (+I effect) is operative in the oxidation of amino alcohols and these facts are supported by the thermodynamic parameters which were calculated from Eyring plots. Each reaction was found to obey the Arrhenius relationship in the temperature range 303–323 K; ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔG^{\ddagger} plot is made from which isokinetic temperature β was evaluated (423 K) which was found to be much above the experimental temperature range indicating that oxidation reactions are enthalpy controlled.

The values of $10^5 k^1/\text{s}^{-1}$ obtained are 4.3 ± 0.15 (35°), 13.8 ± 0.15 (40°), 20.9 ± 0.15 (45°), 42.6 ± 0.15 (50°) with E_{a} 95.7 kJ mol^{-1} , ΔH^{\ddagger} $93.13 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and ΔS^{\ddagger} $-26.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for ethanolamine. The values of $10^5 k^1/\text{s}^{-1}$ are 5.5 ± 0.15 (35°), 24.4 ± 0.15 (40°), 68.3 ± 0.15 (45°), 101 ± 0.15 (50°) with E_{a} $86.13 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, ΔH^{\ddagger} $83.57 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and ΔS^{\ddagger} $-54.9 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for propanolamine. Further values of $10^5 k^1/\text{s}^{-1}$ are 16.76 ± 0.15 (35°), 32.9 ± 0.15 (40°), 46.2 ± 0.15 (45°), 80.4 ± 0.15 (50°) with E_{a} 84.2 kJ mol^{-1} and ΔH^{\ddagger} 81 kJ mol^{-1} and ΔS^{\ddagger} $-51.8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for diethanolamine. The values $10^5 k^1/\text{s}^{-1}$ are 56.2 ± 0.15 (35°), 69.5 ± 0.15 (40°), 89.0 ± 0.15 (45°) and 132.3 ± 0.15 (50°) with E_{a} $63.16 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, ΔH^{\ddagger} 60.6 kJ mol^{-1} and ΔS^{\ddagger} $-108.4 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for triethanolamine. The large negative values of ΔS^{\ddagger} were not uncommon in the literature⁸ these results indicates that greater rigidity of the transition state was formed.

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Stock solution of Ce^{IV} was prepared by dissolving salt of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_6$ A.R. grade (E. Merck) in aqueous HNO_3 . The stock solution was kept at room temperature for 48 h to attain the equilibration. The prepared oxidant was estimated by adding a definite volume of it to a known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and back titrating the unreacted ferrous with standard ceric nitrate

solution using ferroin as an indicator. In the solution, free acid content was estimated by titrating against standard alkali (NaOH) after separation of Ce^{IV} as insoluble Ce^{III} -oxalate, which was formed by the addition of excess $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$. The Ce^{IV} solution in aqueous HNO_3 media is kinetically and thermodynamically stable. The title amino alcohols were of A.R. grade (E. Merck), the stock solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. Weighed amounts of KNO_3 A.R. grade (E. Merck), dissolved in double-distilled water to prepare salt solution to study the salt effect in the present kinetic study. The preparation of Mn^{II} catalyst has been reported earlier⁴.

Procedure and kinetic measurements :

The progress of the reaction was monitored by measuring the change in absorbance at definite time intervals carried out on UV-visible spectrophotometer (Systronics) at λ_{max} 350 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k^1) were calculated from the plot of $\log [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ vs time. The k^1 values were reproducible within experimental ($\pm 2.5\%$). The reactions were studied upto 75–80% completion of the reaction. The kinetic runs were carried out after bubbling nitrogen gas through the reactants present in the reaction vessel. The Ce^{IV} solution under the reaction conditions are thermodynamically and kinetically stable.

Stoichiometry : Under the experimental conditions stoichiometry of Ce^{IV} -AAL redox reaction was determined. Excess concentration of AAL over that Ce^{IV} solution were allowed to react in the presence of Mn^{II} catalyst for 24 h and completion of the reactions was identified by TLC assay. It was found that three moles of Ce^{IV} required for oxidation of ethanolamine, propanolamine six and nine moles of Ce^{IV} required for oxidation of diethanolamine and triethanolamine.

Product analysis : Under the kinetic conditions $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AAL}] = 1.25 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-1}$, $[\text{HNO}_3] = 2.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

for all the amino alcohols the final products were identified as formaldehyde and ammonia by characteristic 2.4 D.N.P. test, and also by chromotropic acid test⁹. And acetaldehyde was formed as additional product in the oxidation of propanolamine.

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